

The final myth and the final truth model:

1. The final value of the true set.
2. Which becomes the final false value
3. The fee: %0.01.
4. Switch the value.
5. Convert the value. 0.91.
6. Switch the value.
7. Convert the value. 0.91.
8. Which becomes the final falser value.
9. Switch the value.
10. Go back to step 9 and seize that value.
11. Go back to step 7 and seize that value.
12. Both those values are the contradiction value.
13. Subtract the twelfth step value from the thirteenth step value.
14. Which becomes the final falsest value.
15. Go back to the step 14 and release that value.
16. Go back to step 8 and release that value.
17. Add the 15th step value with the 16th step value.
18. Which is a value, the finally truest value.

This set is timed as 18:20, and is dated as the 8th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.